

New method for COP optimization in water- and air-cooled single and double effect LiBr-water absorption machines

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Abstract

In this work a new method to optimize the COP in water- and air-cooled single and double effect LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers is proposed. This method determines the effect of condensation temperatures and the solution concentration variation on COP, clearly defining the crystallization limit for different scenarios. This limit is especially important in the design of air-cooled chillers. Taking this into account a simulation program has been developed to calculate the optimum COP. In the case of parallel flow double effect chillers this program estimates not only the optimum COP but also the percentage of refrigerant vapour generated in the high and low temperature desorbers in terms of the condensation temperature. Additionally it provides the mass flow of the solution that should be distributed to each desorber to attain the desired variation in solution concentration.

Keywords: Condenser Water-cooled Air-cooled, Absorption system Lithium bromide COP, Simulation

1. Introduction

Lithium bromide-water is the working pair of choice in many water- and air-cooled single and double effect absorption chillers. At this writing, no air-cooled double effect chillers are available on the market. Where heat exchangers are large, such as in double effect chillers, designing an absorber that can operate efficiently at absorption temperatures of over 45 °C (such as in air-cooled chillers) is a complex undertaking.

The Eduardo Torroja Institute for Construction Science's Heat Pump Laboratory, which forms part of the Institute's Experimental Solar Energy Plant at La Poveda, Madrid, has been developing a new generation of LiBr/water absorption chillers since 2003. These chillers are designed to work in extremely warm weather at condensation temperatures higher than found in commercial chillers. Air-cooled single and double effect prototypes have been built. A new adiabatic absorber that can operate highly efficiently at outdoor temperatures of 42 °C has also been developed (Palacios et al., 2009). Descriptions of these units have been published by

Marcos (2008) and an international patent has been awarded (Izquierdo et al., 2009). The external fluids (water or air) used to cool the absorbers and condensers in these chillers flow in a series configuration.

Water-cooled single effect chillers are the most common type on the market. Analytical models have been developed over the years to evaluate their yield depending on the working pair (Alefeld, 1987; Tufano, 1998); to identify the ideal cycle (Felli, 1983; Tozer and James, 1997); or to predict their performance based on simulation (Hellmann and Ziegler, 1999; Kaynakli and Kilic, 2007). Recently, Kim and Infante Ferreira (2008) published a paper describing single effect chiller performance for different working pairs.

Double effect absorption chillers, in turn, were designed and developed to increase the efficiency of single effect machines. The main structural difference is that they are fitted with two desorbers, also called generators, rather than one. This arrangement delivers more refrigerant, thereby raising chiller efficiency. To this end, the temperature reached in the cycle must be higher than in single effect cycles so the refrigerant vapour generated in the high temperature desorber (HTD) can provide the energy needed to boil the solution flowing through the low temperature desorber (LTD). Single effect chillers operate with a heat source from 70 to 105 °C, whereas double effect machines require a heat source upward of 150 °C (Henning, 2007).

Double effect chillers can be classified by the way the solution (internal fluid) flows through the regenerators and desorbers. In “series flow” double effect chillers, the solution flows successively through the low temperature regenerator (LR), high temperature regenerator (HR), HTD and LTD. In “parallel flow” machines, by contrast, part of the solution flows to the HR/HTD and part to the LR/LTD.

Single effect and double effect series flow cycles have been studied by a number of authors (Anand and Kumar, 1987; Gommed and Grossman, 1990; Arun et al., 2000). More recently, Gomri (2009) and Kaushik and Arora (2009) analyzed these cycles both energetically and exergetically. The condensation temperatures used in their simulations are characteristic of water-cooled chillers, while air-cooled machines are especially useful in dry climates where water is scarce and condensation temperatures may reach values of up to 55 °C (Izquierdo et al., 2004). Since under these conditions the chiller may have to operate in areas of the Dühring diagram close to the crystallization line, the LiBr concentration in the solution must be controlled very strictly. All these researchers calculated the maximum COP in terms of the temperature of the HTD.

The present study aimed to develop a new method for calculating the working conditions that maximize COP in water- and air-cooled single and double effect LiBr/water absorption chillers. This method determines the optimum COP from a different approach: by calculating the effect of the difference in the concentration of the solution in the absorber and desorber on the risk of crystallization. Furthermore, conversely to Gomri (2009) and Kaushik and Arora (2009) who analyzed series flow units and made no mention of external fluids, in the present work the parallel flow configuration was adopted for regenerators and desorbers (further to Herold et al., 1996 and Xu and Dai, 1997) and assuming series flow for the external fluids. This scheme was developed at the Heat Pump Laboratory, where several prototypes are presently in the testing stage.

2. System description

2.1. Single effect chillers

The water- and air-cooled single effect cycles modelled in this work are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The main difference between these schemes and the more traditional cycles used by Gomri (2009) and Kaushik and Arora (2009) is that here the absorber and condenser are cooled by the external fluid *in series*. In water-cooled chillers, the water flows first through the absorber and then the condenser, transferring absorption and condensation heat to the cooling tower (Fig. 1). In air-cooled chillers also, where forced ventilation is used, first the absorber and then the condenser are cooled (Fig. 2). As a result, in both cases, the final absorption temperature, T_{ABS} , is always lower than the condensation temperature, T_{COND} .

Fig. 1 - Water-cooled single effect LiBr-water absorption chiller.

Fig. 2 - Air-cooled single effect LiBr-water absorption chiller.

2.2. Double effect chillers

Figs. 3 and 4 show water- and air-cooled double effect chillers. A parallel flow for the solution has been chosen. According to Arun et al. (2000), parallel flow distribution reduces pressure drops in solution flow. Furthermore, Marcos (2008) reported that parallel flow provides for better control of refrigerant generation, while Herold et al. (1996) showed that COP is higher with parallel than with series flow. On the other hand, series flow was adopted in the present model for the external fluids to reduce the absorption temperature.

Fig. 3 - Water-cooled double effect LiBr-water absorption chiller.

Fig. 4 - Air-cooled double effect LiBr-water absorption chiller.

Fig. 4 - Air-cooled double effect LiBr-water absorption chiller.

Additionally, a sub-cooler is used in these systems to sub-cool the refrigerant condensed in the LTD (and generated in the HTD) to restore the refrigerant thermodynamic conditions before feeding it into the evaporator.

Both cycles are shown in a P - T - X diagram (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 - Dührings chart for the water- and air-cooled double effect cycle ($T_{odb} = 35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

3. Data reduction

The equations primarily describing the absorption chiller operation are based on the principle of mass, energy and species conservation.

3.1. Assumptions

The calculations were performed based on the following assumptions.

- The refrigerant vapour - coming from the HTD - leaves the LTD as a saturated liquid.
- At the evaporator outlet, the refrigerant is a saturated vapour.
- Pressure drops in pipes and other components are negligible.
- All components are externally adiabatic.

The mass and energy balances are discussed in the following section.

3.2. Single effect chillers

The mass and energy balances for single effect chillers have long been known (Herold et al., 1996). The ratio between the mass flows of the solution and the refrigerant can be expressed in terms of the lithium bromide concentration in the absorber and desorber.

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{dsol}}{\dot{m}_r} = \frac{X_D}{X_D - X_{ABS}} \quad (1)$$

The coefficient of performance (COP) is defined as the ratio of useful heat energy transferred to the amount of energy put into the system (Herold et al., 1996; Xu and Dai, 1997; Tozer, 2002). It can be distinguished the thermal COP (Eq. (2)) and the electrical COP (Eq. (3)):

$$COP_{th} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP}}{\dot{Q}_D} \quad (2)$$

$$COP_{el} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP}}{\dot{W}_{aux}} \quad (3)$$

where W_{aux} is the power demand of all auxiliary equipments.

3.3. Double effect chillers

The mass and energy balances for the more general case, double effect chillers, are described below.

3.3.1. High temperature desorber (HTD)

This component receives heat from exhaust gas, fossil fuel combustion, thermal oil or high temperature fluids heated by solar energy. The heat is used to boil the LiBr/water solution and generate refrigerant vapour. The HTD mass and energy balances can be expressed as follows:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{HTD}} + \dot{m}_{11}h_{11} - \dot{m}_{\text{r1H}}h_{1\text{H}} - \dot{m}_{12}h_{12} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{m}_{11} = \dot{m}_{\text{r1H}} + \dot{m}_{12} \quad (5)$$

$$X_{12}\dot{m}_{12} = X_{11}\dot{m}_{11} \quad (6)$$

Eqs. (5) and (6) yield the relationship between the mass flow of the solution pumped to the HTD and the mass flow of the refrigerant divided between the two desorbers:

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{11}}{\dot{m}_{\text{r1H}}} = \frac{X_{12}}{X_{12} - X_{11}} \quad (7)$$

Operating with Eqs. (4)-(7) yields Eq. (8):

$$\dot{m}_{\text{r1H}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{HTD}}}{\left[\frac{X_{12}}{X_{12} - X_{11}} \cdot (h_{12} - h_{11}) + (h_{1\text{H}} - h_{12}) \right]} \quad (8)$$

i.e., the mass flow of the refrigerant generated in the HTD.

3.3.2. Low temperature desorber (LTD)

The heat source for this desorber is the refrigerant vapour generated in the HTD, which transfers its latent heat to the solution and flows out of the LTD as a saturated liquid. In other words, the LTD also works as a condenser, contributing to a reduction in chiller size and weight. This vapour provides the energy to boil the solution and produce more refrigerant, which is added to the refrigerant generated in the HTD.

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{LTD}} + \dot{m}_8h_8 - \dot{m}_{\text{r1L}}h_{1\text{L}} - \dot{m}_9h_9 = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{m}_8 = \dot{m}_{\text{r1L}} + \dot{m}_9 \quad (10)$$

$$X_9\dot{m}_9 = X_8\dot{m}_8 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\dot{m}_8}{\dot{m}_{\text{r1L}}} = \frac{X_9}{X_9 - X_8} \quad (12)$$

As in the case of LTD, Eq. (13) is obtained

$$\dot{m}_{\text{r1L}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{LTD}}}{\left[\frac{X_9}{X_9 - X_8} \cdot (h_9 - h_8) + (h_{1\text{L}} - h_9) \right]} \quad (13)$$

to determine the mass flow of the refrigerant generated in the LTD. The energy balance for the LTD can be expressed as:

$$\dot{Q}_{LTD} = \dot{m}_{r1H} \cdot (h_{1H} - h_{1CH}) \quad (14)$$

The mass flow of the refrigerant produced by the LTD is found from Eqs. (13) and (14):

$$\dot{m}_{r1L} = \frac{\dot{m}_{r1H} \cdot (h_{1H} - h_{1CH})}{\left[\frac{X_9}{X_9 - X_8} \cdot (h_9 - h_8) + (h_{1L} - h_9) \right]} \quad (15)$$

The refrigerant condensed in the LTD at temperature 1CH (Fig. 3), flows through a liquid sub-cooler where it is cooled to the same condensation temperature as the refrigerant in the LTD.

The mass balance calculated at the pump (Fig. 4) is used to find the relationship between the total mass flow of the solution and the mass flow taken in by each desorber:

$$\dot{m}_5 = \dot{m}_8 + \dot{m}_{11} \quad (16)$$

3.3.3. Absorber (ABS)

A standard falling film absorber was chosen for the model. The respective energy balance is:

$$\dot{Q}_{ABS} = \dot{m}_{14}h_{14} + \dot{m}_{16}h_{16} + \dot{m}_4h_4 - \dot{m}_5h_5 \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{m}_r = \dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_{r1H} + \dot{m}_{r1L} \quad (18)$$

where the total mass flow of the refrigerant produced, m_r , is the sum of the refrigerant flowing to the HTD, m_{r1H} , and the refrigerant flowing to the LTD, m_{r1L} .

Mass balance calculations for the “hot” sides of the HR (Eq. (19)) and LR (Eq. (20)) can be used to determine the total mass flow of the solution returning to the absorber (Eq. (21)):

$$\dot{m}_{11} = \dot{m}_{14} + \dot{m}_{r1H} \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{m}_8 = \dot{m}_{16} + \dot{m}_{r1L} \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{m}_{14} + \dot{m}_{16} = \dot{m}_{11} + \dot{m}_8 \quad (\dot{m}_{r1H} + \dot{m}_{r1L}) \quad (21)$$

3.3.4. Condenser (COND)

The change in refrigerant phase (from vapour to liquid) takes place in the condenser, whose energy balance can be expressed as:

$$\dot{Q}_{COND} = \dot{m}_{r1L} (h_{1L} - h_2) \quad (22)$$

3.3.5. Sub-cooler (SUB)

When the refrigerant generated in the HTD leaves the LTD (point 1CH) in a saturated liquid state it needs to be cooled to the working conditions in the evaporator. Such cooling takes place in a heat exchanger called sub-cooler, which is separated from the condenser. The energy balance for this component is:

$$\dot{Q}_{SUB} = \dot{m}_{r1H} (h_{1CH} - h_2) \quad (23)$$

where Q_C is the sum of sub-cooling and condensation heat.

$$\dot{Q}_C = \dot{Q}_{COND} + \dot{Q}_{SUB} \quad (24)$$

3.3.6. Evaporator (EVAP)

The evaporator is the component where the liquid refrigerant boils as a result of the low pressure and the heat transferred by the external fluid (water or air), which is cooled in the process. The latent vaporization heat (useful heat energy transferred) is found as follows,

$$\dot{Q}_{EVAP} = (\dot{m}_{rIH} + \dot{m}_{rIL}) \cdot (h_3 - h_4) = \dot{m}_r \cdot (h_3 - h_4) \quad (25)$$

3.3.7. High temperature regenerator (HR)

The high temperature regenerator (HR) is a heat exchanger located between the absorber and the HTD. Its purpose is to recover the heat coming from the concentrated solution at the HTD outlet and use it to preheat the diluted solution before it flows into the HTD. The effectiveness of this heat exchanger as well as the diluted concentrated solution temperature is given by Eq. (26):

$$\xi_{HR} = \frac{t_{12} - t_{13}}{t_{12} - t_{10}} \quad (26)$$

The effectiveness assumed for the regenerator in this work was 0.7.

$$t_{13} = t_{12} - \xi_{HR}(t_{12} - t_{10})$$

The heat recovered is found from:

$$\dot{Q}_{HR} = \dot{m}_{11} \cdot c_p(X_{ABS}) \cdot (t_{11} - t_{10}) = \dot{m}_{11} \cdot (h_{11} - h_{10}) \quad (27)$$

where the temperature of the diluted solution at the HTD inlet is:

$$t_{11} = t_{10} + \frac{\dot{Q}_{HR}}{\dot{m}_{11} \cdot c_p(X_{ABS})} \quad (28)$$

3.3.8. Low temperature regenerator (LR)

The purpose of this regenerator is the same as in the HR: to preheat the diluted solution before it flows into the LTD and thereby cools the concentrated solution when it returns to the absorber.

Operating as above for the HR yields:

$$\xi_{LR} = \frac{t_9 - t_{15}}{t_9 - t_7} \quad (29)$$

$$t_{15} = t_9 - \xi_{LR}(t_9 - t_7) \quad (30)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{LR} = \dot{m}_7 \cdot c_p(X_{ABS}) \cdot (t_8 - t_7) = \dot{m}_7 \cdot (h_8 - h_7) \quad (31)$$

The expression used to calculate the temperature of the solution at the LR outlet can be deduced from Eq. (32):

$$t_8 = t_6 + \frac{\dot{Q}_{LR}}{\dot{m}_7 \cdot c_p(X_{ABS})} \quad (32)$$

3.3.9. Expansion valves

The expansion valves cause a temperature and pressure drop in the liquid refrigerant at the evaporator inlet. One expansion valve is located at the condenser outlet and another at the sub-cooler outlet. At the valve outlet, the refrigerant is a two-phase mix. This process is

isenthalpic:

$$h_2 = h_3$$

The concentrated solution from the regenerators flows through these valves, where the pressure drops, to the absorber. This process is likewise isenthalpic:

$$h_{13} = h_{14}$$

$$h_{15} = h_{16}$$

3.3.10. Pump

The pump that drives the solution must be able to exceed the pressure drops in all the components, maintaining a constant pressure in the desorbers. The work performed by the pump is as follows:

$$W_p = \frac{v \cdot (p_6 - p_5)}{\eta_p}$$

where a pump efficiency (η_p) of 70% is adopted, while pump power is:

$$\dot{W}_p = \dot{m}_5 \cdot W_p$$

3.3.11. Cooling tower

The cooling tower transfers the absorption and condensation heat to the atmosphere. In the present design the cooling water flows through the absorber, condenser and sub-cooler in series (in that order). The energy balance for the cooling tower can be expressed as:

$$\dot{Q}_{ABS} + \dot{Q}_{COND} + \dot{Q}_{SUB} = \dot{m}_{cw} \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{cw,i} - T_{cw,o})$$

Eq. (38) can be used to calculate the mass flow of cooling water needed to cool these three components:

$$\dot{m}_{cw} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{ABS} + \dot{Q}_{COND} + \dot{Q}_{SUB}}{c_p \cdot (T_{cw,i} - T_{cw,o})} \quad (39)$$

3.3.12. Coefficient of performance (COP)

COP is defined as above, for a single effect chiller (Eq. (2)). In double effect chillers, the heat transferred to the desorber is the heat supplied to the HTD: $Q_D = Q_{HTD}$. Furthermore, the useful heat energy transferred in the evaporator can be divided between:

- the contribution of the refrigerant generated in the HTD (Q_{EVAP_HTD}), and
- the contribution of the refrigerant generated in the LTD (Q_{EVAP_LTD}).

Substituting these two expressions into Eq. (2) yields the following thermal and electrical COP:

$$COP_{th} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP}}{\dot{Q}_D} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP_HTD} + \dot{Q}_{EVAP_LTD}}{\dot{Q}_{HTD}} = COP_{th,EVAP_HTD} + COP_{th,EVAP_LTD} \quad (40)$$

$$COP_{el} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP}}{\dot{W}_{aux}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{EVAP_HTD} + \dot{Q}_{EVAP_LTD}}{\dot{W}_{aux}} = COP_{el,EVAP_HTD} + COP_{el,EVAP_LTD} \quad (41)$$

4. COP optimization

The parameter chosen as a reference to optimize chiller operation and maximize COP was the variation in solution concentration, ΔX . This choice is justified by the important role that solution concentration plays in chiller, especially air-cooled chiller, performance. The difference between the concentration of the solution in the desorber and the absorber is essential to ensure proper chiller operation. This calls for clearly defining the crystallization limit in terms of ΔX . Moreover, the value of ΔX that optimizes COP has been shown to suffer small variations even under widely fluctuating weather conditions (Marcos, 2008). For all the foregoing, ΔX is a most suitable choice as the reference variable for optimizing COP.

4.1. Single effect

The rate at which heat is transferred to the solution in the desorber is calculated by obtaining the mass flow of the refrigerant, \dot{m}_R , from Eq. (1) and substituting it into the energy balance equation for the desorber:

$$\dot{Q}_D = \dot{m}_{dsol} \frac{X_D}{X_{ABS}} (h_1 - h_8) + \dot{m}_{dsol} (h_8 - h_7) \quad (42)$$

where: $\Delta X = X_D - X_{ABS}$

Using the mass and energy balances for single effect cycles and assuming:

- $T_{EVAP} = 5^\circ\text{C}$ for water-cooled chillers
- $T_{EVAP} = 6^\circ\text{C}, 8^\circ\text{C}$ and 10°C , for air-cooled chillers, with $T_{COND} = 45^\circ\text{C}, 50^\circ\text{C}$ and 55°C , respectively.
- Regenerator effectiveness = 0.7
- Safety margin for the crystallization limit of 1.5%.

An application was developed with EES software (Klein, 2009) to maximize COP in terms of ΔX at different condensation temperatures. For the water-cooled chiller, the T_{COND} used were $25^\circ\text{C}, 30^\circ\text{C}, 35^\circ\text{C}$ and 40°C (Fig. 5), while for the air-cooled chiller the values were $45^\circ\text{C}, 50^\circ\text{C}$ and 55°C (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 - COP vs. ΔX (a) and COP vs. T_8 (b) in a water-cooled single effect absorption chiller.

According to Fig. 6a, in a water-cooled single effect chiller, the maximum COP is attained when ΔX is 6.7%, 7.5%, 8.3% and 9.5% for condensation temperatures of $25^\circ\text{C}, 30^\circ\text{C}, 35^\circ\text{C}$ and 40°C , respectively. In this case the risk of crystallization is negligible at the three lowest condensation temperatures ($25^\circ\text{C}, 30^\circ\text{C}$ and 35°C) because the crystallization limit is 15.5%, 12.3% and 9.5%, respectively. When $T_{COND} = 40^\circ\text{C}$, however, the optimum ΔX value, 9.5%, exceeds the crystallization limit, 7% and consequently, this will be the threshold of operation which defines the ΔX value that optimizes the COP. This, then, is the highest ΔX value that optimizes COP. The optimal COP values for these T_{COND} are 0.85, 0.82, 0.78 and 0.74, respectively. In order to obtain these values, it is necessary to reach the following temperatures in the desorber: $57.8^\circ\text{C}, 71.9^\circ\text{C}, 85.6^\circ\text{C}$ and 92.8°C , respectively (Fig 6b).

The optimal COP scenario for an air-cooled single effect chiller in the condensation temperature range chosen, $45^\circ\text{C}, 50^\circ\text{C}$ and 55°C , is similar (Fig. 7). In this case, all the optimal values found with the simulation

exceed the crystallization limit. That limit, therefore, defines the $6X$ value that maximizes COP. In other words, for $T_{COND}=45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, optimal COP values of 0.72, 0.69 and 0.65 are reached when ΔX equals 6.5%, 5% and 3.9%, respectively (Fig. 7a). To achieve the aforementioned values, the temperatures required in the desorber are the following: $98.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $104.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $110.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively (Fig. 7b).

Fig. 7 - COP vs. ΔX (a) and COP vs. T_8 (b) in an air-cooled single effect absorption chiller.

4.2. Validation of the single effect simulation

Model validation entails comparing the theoretical results obtained with the simulation to experimental findings. To this purpose, two works from the representative of the state of art published by Syed et al. (2005) and Li and Sumathy (2001) have been selected and compared it with the results obtained before (see Table 1).

Parameters: $T_{amb} = 34\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_{COND} = 29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_{EVAP} = 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_D = 64\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $\dot{Q}_{EVAP} = 7.5\text{ kW}$				
	Syed et al. (2005)	Present paper	Difference	Optimum
\dot{Q}_D (kW)	12.5	10	2.5	9
COP_{th}^a	0.6	0.8	0.2	0.82
Parameters: $T_{amb} = 33\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_{COND} = 29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_{EVAP} = 6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_D = 73\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $\dot{Q}_{EVAP} = 4.7\text{ kW}$				
	Li and Sumathy (2001)	Present paper	Difference	Optimum
\dot{Q}_D (kW)	8.3	5.7	2.6	5.6
COP_{th}^a	0.57	0.8	0.23	0.83

^a COP calculated excluding the power demand of the auxiliary equipment.

Table 1.- Model validation for a single effect chiller

The reason for the difference between the simulated and experimental results shown in Table 1 is the heat losses occurred in the desorber and the evaporator. Furthermore, Syed et al. (2005) tested a WFC10 35-kW absorption chiller operating at a partial load of approximately 25%. Table 1 also shows that, while according to the experimental findings the amount of power that needed to be transferred in the desorber (Q_D) was 12.5 kW, the simulation called for only 10 kW. The final column in the table gives the optimal working values, which would be attained at a ΔX of approximately 7.5%.

4.3. Double effect

The simulation program that optimizes the COP in double effect cycles is more complex because it has two desorbers that generate refrigerant vapour. The interdependence between the refrigerant generated in the two desorbers must first be determined. The mass flow of the refrigerant vapour

generated by the HTD and the LTD is calculated from Eqs. (7) and (12). Both mass flows depend on the absorber and desorber lithium bromide concentration, as well as on the heat transfer rate supplied to each desorber. These values are also impacted by refrigerant enthalpy at the outlet of HTD, h_{1H} , and LTD, h_{1L} , and by the solution enthalpy at the end of the boiling process in each desorber, h_{12} and h_9 .

Eqs. (7) and (12) can be used to obtain the following expressions, which relate the mass flows of the solution and the refrigerant at HTD (Eq. (43)) and LTD (Eq. (44)).

$$\frac{X_{12}}{X_{12} - X_{11}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{HTD}}{\dot{m}_{r1H}} \frac{(h_{1H} - h_{12})}{(h_{12} - h_{11})} \quad (43)$$

$$\frac{X_9}{X_9 - X_8} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{LTD}}{\dot{m}_{r1L}} \frac{(h_{1L} - h_9)}{(h_9 - h_8)} \quad (44)$$

where: $\Delta X_{HTD} = X_{12} - X_{11}$; and $\Delta X_{LTD} = X_9 - X_8$.

The final concentration in each desorber can be expressed in terms of the initial concentration as follows:

$$X_{12} = \frac{X_{11}}{1 - \frac{\dot{Q}_{HTD}}{\dot{m}_{r1H}} \frac{(h_{1H} - h_{12})}{(h_{12} - h_{11})}} \quad (45)$$

$$X_9 = \frac{X_8}{1 - \frac{\dot{Q}_{LTD}}{\dot{m}_{r1L}} \frac{(h_{1L} - h_9)}{(h_9 - h_8)}} \quad (46)$$

provided that, in Eqs. (45) and (46): $X_{12} > X_{11}$; $X_9 > X_8$, and the heat transferred in both desorbers meets the following conditions:

$$\dot{Q}_{HTD} > \dot{m}_{r1H}(h_{1H} - h_{11}) \quad (47)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{LTD} > \dot{m}_{r1L}(h_{1L} - h_8) \quad (48)$$

Moreover, since Q_{EVAP} is known to vary with outdoor temperature and Q_{HTD} and Q_{LTD} also depend on Q_{EVAP} , the COP at any instant can be obtained in terms of the respective variations in solution concentrations, ΔX_{HTD} and ΔX_{LTD} . Three possible scenarios can therefore be considered:

$$\Delta X_{HTD} = \Delta X_{LTD}$$

$$\Delta X_{HTD} > \Delta X_{LTD}$$

$$\Delta X_{HTD} < \Delta X_{LTD}$$

Pursuant to Eqs. (6) and (12), the mass flow of the refrigerant produced by the desorbers rises with ΔX_{HTD} and ΔX_{LTD} when Q_{HTD} and Q_{LTD} remain constant. Since ΔX_{HTD} and ΔX_{LTD} can only be simultaneously maximized in case (a), this is the scenario used in the following discussion.

Under these conditions, a simulation application was developed with EES software based on the equations in Section 3 above (subject to the limitations set out in Eqs. (43)-(48)) and adding to the previously mentioned hypothesis for single effect, the following new hypothesis: $\Delta X_{HTD} = \Delta X_{LTD}$. This program calculates the variation in concentration solution that maximizes COP under changing conditions.

When $\Delta X_{HTD} = \Delta X_{LTD}$, the second terms of Eqs. (7) and (11) are equal, and hence:

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{11}}{\dot{m}_8} = \frac{\dot{m}_{r1H}}{\dot{m}_{r1L}} \quad (49)$$

Tozer and James (1997) symbolized the theoretical refrigerant in a single effect LiBr/H₂O chiller with the parameter α (<1); and on those grounds defined the refrigerant in a double effect machine as $\alpha + \alpha^2$, to take account of the refrigerant produced in the LTD. On those grounds, the mass flow of the refrigerant generated in the HTD may be deduced to be higher than the mass flow of the refrigerant generated in the LTD. Consequently, further to Eq. (48), the mass flow of the solution streaming through the HTD, m_{11} , is greater than the flow of the solution flowing across the LTD, m_8 .

One of the objectives of the present study was to establish the relationship between m_{F1A} and m_{F1B} in terms of the variation in the concentration of the solution in each desorber, ΔX in a double effect chiller operating under real conditions, as well as the relationships among these three parameters. A subroutine was consequently developed (within the main program) to find that relationship with an iterative procedure. The thermodynamic properties of the LiBr/H₂O solution were found from the correlations proposed by Pátek and Klomfar (2006).

The results showed that the percentage of refrigerant generated by the HTD ranges from 53% (when $m_{dsol_HTD} / m_{dsol_LTD} = m_{11} / m_8 = 1.14$ and the condensation temperature is 25°C), to a maximum value of 55% (when $m_{dsol_HTD} / m_{dsol_LTD} = m_{11} / m_8 = 1.25$ and the condensation temperature is 40°C). In air-cooled chillers, these percentages range from 56% (when $m_{dsol_HTD} / m_{dsol_LTD} = m_{11} / m_8 = 1.27$ and the condensation temperature is 45°C) to 57% (when $m_{dsol_HTD} / m_{dsol_LTD} = m_{11} / m_8 = 1.32$ and the condensation temperature is 55°C). The program was run for water-cooled double effect machines with the same four condensation temperatures as for single effect (25°C, 30°C, 35°C and 40°C). The results are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 8a shows that the optimum COP is obtained when ΔX equals 9.0%, 9.4%, 10.2% and 11% when $T_{COND} = 25^\circ\text{C}$, 30°C , 35°C and 40°C , respectively. As observed in the simulation for the single effect chiller, however, the ΔX values for $T_{COND} = 35^\circ\text{C}$ and 40°C exceed the crystallization limits of 9.5% and 7%. Therefore, the latter two values are defined to be the ΔX values that optimize COP for those condensation temperatures. The optimal COP values for the four T_{COND} are 1.48, 1.38, 1.29 and 1.20, respectively. These values were obtained by reaching temperatures of 108.7°C, 133.6°C, 157.5°C and 164.3°C, respectively, in the desorber (Fig. 8b).

Fig. 8 - COP vs. ΔX (a) and COP vs. T_{12} (b) in a water-cooled double effect absorption chiller.

The optimum COP for an air-cooled double effect chiller, in tum, is limited by the crystallization limit, as observed for single effect chillers. For $T_{COND} = 45^\circ\text{C}$, 50°C and 55°C , optimal COP values of approximately 1.15, 1.07 and 0.98 are reached when ΔX equals 6.5%, 5% and 3.9%, respectively (Fig. 9a). The findings delivered by the main program further show that for low values of ΔX , the mass flow of the solution through both desorbers (Eqs. (7) and (12)) is very high, an indication of low COP values.

The desorber temperatures required to reach these COP values are 171.1°C, 179.4°C and 186.3°C, respectively (Fig. 9b).

Fig. 9 - COP vs. ΔX (a) and COP vs. T_{12} (b) in an air-cooled double effect absorption chiller.

4.4. Validation of the double effect simulation

The model proposed for double effect chillers was validated by comparing the simulated findings to experimental results with an air-cooled double effect prototype reported by Marcos (2008) {see Table 2}.

As Table 2 shows, the COP reported by Marcos (2008) is 0.85 and the theoretical COP computed by the model proposed under the same conditions comes to 0.87. Here the difference between the experimental and theoretical value of Q_{HTD} is negligible, at 0.1 kW. The optimal COP, in turn, at 1.14, would be attained for a ΔX value of approximately 6.5%. This value could be achieved increasing the desorber temperature to 170.4 °C.

Parameters: $T_{amb} = 32\text{ °C}$; $T_{COND} = 44\text{ °C}$; $T_{EVAP} = 5\text{ °C}$;
 $T_{HTD} = 164\text{ °C}$; $Q_{EVAP} = 4\text{ kW}$

	Marcos (2008)	Present paper	Difference	Optimum
\dot{Q}_{HTD} (kW)	4	3.9	0.1	2.7
COP ^a	0.85	0.87	0.02	1.14

^a COP calculated excluding the power demand of the auxiliary equipment.

Table 2. – Model validation for a double effect chiller

5. Conclusions

The new method proposed has proven able to correctly predict the parameters that optimize COP in water- and air- cooled single and double effect LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers. The effect of the condensation and desorption temperatures on COP, and particularly the effect of the variation in solution concentration, ΔX , were studied. Moreover, the crystallization limit (McNeely, 1979) for different scenarios was clearly defined. This limit is especially important in air-cooled chiller design. A simulation program developed for parallel flow double effect chillers predicts the percentage of refrigerant vapour generated in the HLD and the LTD in terms of the condensation temperature. Finally, the program also yields the mass flow of the solution that should be distributed to each desorber to attain the desired variation in solution concentration. The results obtained are summarized as below.

- In water-cooled single effect chillers, the maximum COP for T_{COND} of 25 °C, 30 °C, 35 °C and 40 °C is reached when ΔX is 6.7%, 7.5%, 8.3% and 7%, respectively. The optimal COP values range from 0.85 to 0.74 with desorber temperatures ranging from 57.8 °C to 92.8 °C. In air-cooled single effect chillers, the maximum COP for T_{COND} of 45 °C, 50 °C and 55 °C is attained when ΔX is 6.5%, 5% and 3.9%, respectively; the respective COP values range from 0.72 to 0.65, and the desorber temperatures from 98.5 °C to 110.1 °C.
- In water-cooled double effect chillers COP is maximized at T_{COND} of 25°C, 30 °C, 35 °C and 40 °C when ΔX is 9.0%, 9.4%, 9.5% and 7%, respectively. The optimal COP values range from 1.48 to 1.2, with desorber

temperatures between 108.7 °C and 164.3 °C. In air-cooled double effect chillers, optimal COP is attained at T_{COND} of 45 °C, 50 °C and 55 °C when ΔX equals 6.5%, 5% and 3.9%. The COP values are 1.15, 1.07 and 0.98 when T_{EVAP} is 6 °C, 8 °C and 10 °C, respectively. The driving temperatures in the desorber varied from 171.1 °C to 186.3 °C.

- In water-cooled double effect chillers ($T_{COND}=25-40$ °C), the HID is found to generate from 53% to 55% of the total refrigerant. In air-cooled machines ($T_{COND}=45-55$ °C), the HTD generates from 56% to 57% of the total refrigerant.
- The optimal HTD to LTD mass flow ratio in water-cooled chillers range from 1.14 to 1.25; and in air-cooled units from 1.27 to 1.32.

Nomenclature

ABS	absorber
COND	condenser
COP	coefficient of performance
c_p	specific heat at constant pressure (kJ kg ⁻¹)
D	desorber or generator
EVAP	evaporator
HTD	high temperature desorber
LTD	low temperature desorber
h	specific enthalpy (kJ kg ⁻¹)
HR	high temperature regenerator
LR	low temperature regenerator
m	mass flow (kg s ⁻¹)
p	pressure (kPa)
Q	heat transfer rate (W)
R	regenerator
SUB	sub-cooler
T, t	temperature (°C)
v	specific volume (m ³ kg ⁻¹)
w	specific work (kJ kg ⁻¹)
W	power (W)
X	mass fraction of LiBr (%)

Greek letters

ξ	effectiveness
η	efficiency

Subscripts

aux	auxiliary equipment
C	sum of condensation plus sub-cooling heat
cw	cooling water
dsol	diluted solution
el	electrical
i	inlet
r	refrigerant
o	outlet
odb	outdoor dry bulb
p	pump
th	thermal

Acknowledgements

This study was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Technology under INVISIO Project PSE-380000-2007-2/2008-6. The authors wish to thank Professors S.A. Klein and G.F. Nellis of the University of Wisconsin's Solar Energy Laboratory for their mentoring and support.

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